

ADDITIONAL INFORMATION

Calculation of the number ratio of ¹¹¹In nuclides and micelles

For the calculation of the number of micelles we have used the aggregation number from the publication by Wilhelm et al.²⁵ For a PS-b-PEO block copolymer with a comparable size, i.e. for PS-b-PEO 11200-17500 an average aggregation number of 290 have been reported. At a PS-b-PEO 9500-18000 concentration of 1.1 mg/mL in a default volume 2.3 mL the number of micelles will be:

$$\frac{1.1 \times 10^{-3} \text{ g/mL} \times 2.3 \text{ mL}}{(9500 + 18000) \text{ g/mole}} \times \frac{6.022 \times 10^{23} \text{ n/mole}}{290 \text{ n/micelle}} = 1.91 \times 10^{14} \text{ micelles}$$

The number of ¹¹¹In nuclides is directly proportional to the activity and can be calculated with the decay constant, λ , which for ¹¹¹In is $2.86 \times 10^{-6} \text{ s}^{-1}$. At 50 MBq the number of ¹¹¹In atoms is:

$$N = \frac{A}{\lambda} = \frac{50 \times 10^6 \text{ s}^{-1}}{2.86 \times 10^{-6} \text{ s}^{-1}} = 1.74 \times 10^{13} \text{ atoms}$$

In this example there is about ten times excess of micelles compared to the number of ¹¹¹In atoms, meaning that part of the micelles will not contain any ¹¹¹In.